

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF EFFECTIVENESS OF SACROILIAC JOINT TREATMENT USING THE METHODS OF JAMES CYRIAX, BRIAN MULLIGAN AND MASAYUKI SAIONJI

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Abstract

Introduction. Initially it was believed that there was no mobility within the sacroiliac joints. However, as present experience shows, not only is there mobility, but movements within this joint exert enormous influence on the efficiency of the connection between the spine and the lower limbs. The methods of James Cyriax, Brian Mulligan, and Masayuki Saionji (Yumeiho) exemplify use of manual therapy techniques affecting the sacroiliac joints and periarticular tissue. The present study compares the efficiency of the above methods in the treatment of sacroiliac joints. This is done by showing the efficiency of each method separately, and by presenting a subsequent comparison of the results obtained.

Methods. The study was based on an experiment carried out on a group of forty-five volunteers, differentiated with regard to sex, age, and occupational structure. The key selectional criterion was occurrence of disorders within the sacroiliac joints in a patient, which had to be confirmed by positive results in five tests evaluating the positioning of the pelvic girdle. Each study subject was then randomly selected for a series of at least three procedures in one of the three manual therapy methods. An evaluation of the efficiency of the respective techniques was carried out based on the five evaluative tests mentioned above.

Results. Initially, all of the patients demonstrated pelvic torsion. After the last procedure in the series, regardless of the method employed, the torsion subsided in all patients. These results were then verified statistically using chi-square distribution, which revealed no differences between the efficiency of the methods under comparison. At the same time, the study proved that all three manual therapy methods are very effective in removing pelvic torsion in patients.

Conclusions. The analysis showed no significant differences between the therapeutic methods studied (the methods of Mulligan, Cyriax and Yumeiho) with respect to treatment of sacroiliac joints, despite the fact that each method uses different techniques.

1. Introduction

It was initially believed that there was no mobility within the sacroiliac joints. For this reason, these joints have largely remained outside the scope of interest of most medical specialties dealing with the organ of locomotion. Outside the field of manual medicine, the function of the sacroiliac joints is generally little known and underappreciated. However, the experience of manual therapists, chiropractors and osteopaths demonstrates that not only does movement occur within these joints, but it has a profound influence on the efficiency of the connection between the spine and the lower limbs. In recent times, there has been increased interest in the sacroiliac joints and their role in the functioning of the organ of locomotion.

Manual therapy methods that employ techniques affecting the sacroiliac joints and periarticular tissues include the methods of James Cyriax, Brian Mulligan, and Masayuki Saionji (Yumeiho). A comparison of the efficiency of these methods is based on our own experiment, carried out on a pre-selected study group.

Pathologies within the sacroiliac joints

The sacroiliac joint, as other joints, may be subject to various types of pathologies. These may be caused by various traumas, including twists, sprains and fractures. Speaking of pathologies affecting sacroiliac joints, we also need to mention a group of very serious joint diseases, including inflammatory, hyperplastic and developmental disorders – caused by various local or generalized processes within the body. The causes may include ankylosing and rheumatoid diseases of the joints, neoplastic diseases, inflammatory diseases of the bones and joints, osteoporosis, developmental disorders and others (Stodolny 1999). Each of these conditions undoubtedly deserves a separate study. Nonetheless, they are beyond the immediate scope of this paper, which is why only functional disorders in the sacroiliac joints will be dealt with here.

Functional disorders affecting the sacroiliac joints are decidedly the commonest cause of pain ailments of the organ of locomotion. The most frequent symptom of reversible functional disorders in the locomotor system, and thus also in the sacroiliac joint, is blockage. This disorder may occur in the sacroiliac joint with limited or excessive mobility and is characterized by such symptoms as the ones listed below:

- limitations of mobility within the joint with the following characteristics:
 - a quantitative limitation in mobility, measurable in angular degrees or centimeters;
 - a qualitative limitation in mobility, with impaired articular play and altered final resistance;
- possible occurrence of points of excessive sensitivity to pressure (trigger points);
 - frequent occurrence of pain at rest and/or in motion (Arkuszewski 2001).

According to Neumann, the term *blockage* denotes:

- a reversible disorder of articular activity, characterized by limited mobility; the limitation may occur at any point in the physiological motion trajectory, from the neutral position to the final point; mobility is not totally impossible in one or several directions; articular play is impaired as a rule;
- by way of a neurophysiological reflex, increased tension occurs in the muscles, inhibiting motion in the direction of the blockage;
- disorders in the functioning of soft tissues and internal organs segmentally connected to the given joint are detectable (Neumann 1992).

In sum, acute blockages in the sacroiliac joints, apart from pain ailments, result also in an asymmetry of the pelvic girdle, which adversely affects the spine and the lower limbs.

The last thing worth mentioning is occurrence of hyper-mobility within sacroiliac joints. Despite the fact that hyper-mobility is not a disease or a pathological state of the organ of locomotion, it may result in significant adverse effects (Stodolny 1999). A hyper-mobile sacroiliac joint, when a static posture is maintained for extended periods, poses a risk of chronic pain, and of recurring episodes of acute blockage (Hartman 1997).

Purpose of the study

The aim of the present study is assessing the effectiveness of the above-mentioned therapeutic methods in the treatment of sacroiliac joints by demonstrating the efficiency of each method separately and then by comparing the results.

Our own study, performed on a selected group at manual therapy office “Condylus” provides a basis for estimating the effects brought by the application of the respective procedures. The study covered the period from March 1, 2008 to March 01, 2009. The patients included in the study group displayed sacroiliac joint disorders, resulting in improper positioning of the pelvis. The aim of the study is demonstrating that procedures utilizing the respective therapeutic techniques performed in the study should, by assumption, improve the positioning of the pelvis.

By providing a clear, experiment-based comparison of the efficiency of the three methods, the study should provide new knowledge on the efficiency of each method separately, in the treatment of sacroiliac joint disorders. This will expand the existing knowledge concerning the effectiveness of each of the methods, as no similar experiments have been carried out to date, and there are no comparative studies contrasting these three manual therapy methods.

2. Material and methods

Description of the study group

A manual test of the sacroiliac joints was carried out on a group of forty-five volunteers, of which twenty were women (45%), and 25 were men (55%). The youngest participant was 21 years old, and the oldest 61. The majority of the study subjects were young people, and only one-third of the group were aged over 40, and five persons were aged 50 and more. Most of the participants were inhabitants of the city of Bydgoszcz (71%), and only five patients participating in the study came

from outside the Kujawsko-Pomorskie province. The study did not include pregnant women.

With regard to occupational structure, the group was fairly varied – including both people who worked intensely with their bodies, such as circus acrobats, a dance instructor, a P. E. teacher – and persons with more sedentary work, such as an IT specialist and a driver. The group also included eight students, a doctoral candidate, several teachers, salespeople, economists, managers and physical workers – working in construction, wholesale stores and warehouses.

Method of selecting the participants

The study group was selected out of people who came to the manual therapy office for treatment. All of the participants gave their written consent for participation in the study and received a leaflet with information concerning the study. The first selectional criterion was that the participants be adults. The second criterion was that the patient exhibit disorders within the sacroiliac joints, confirmed by positive results in five tests:

- a test for the asymmetry in the positioning of the anterior superior spines, performed on the patient lying on the back, and the influence of this positioning on the apparent shortening or elongation of the lower limbs (photograph 1),

Photograph 1. A test for asymmetry in the positioning of the anterior superior spines.

- a test for the asymmetry in the positioning of the posterior inferior spines with the patient lying prone, and the influence of this positioning on the apparent shortening or elongation of the lower limbs,
- standing flexion test – a test of the functioning of the sacroiliac joint (photograph 2),

Photograph 2. Standing flexion test

- Gillet's reaction test – a test of the function of the sacroiliac joint (photograph 3),

Photograph 3. Gillet's reaction

- Derbolowsky's reaction test – an evaluation of the change in the length of the lower limbs – flexion test in with the patient prone (photograph 4) (Buckup 2007).

Photograph 4. Derbolowsky's reaction

The patients in whom one limb was anatomically shorter were not qualified for the study group. Pain ailments reported by patients as well as scoliosis did not disqualify patients from participation in the study.

Methods

Forty-five patients were qualified for the study. Each of them was subsequently qualified to undergo a series of procedures following one of the three therapeutic methods:

- James Cyriax's method,
- Brian Mulligan's method,
- Masayuki Sainoji's Yumeiho method.

The selection of the method for each patient was random.

As a result, three fifteen-person groups were constituted, and their members underwent a series of at least three procedures in a pre-selected manual therapy method. If the series of procedures administered to a given patient included more than three sessions, then the results of the fourth and subsequent sessions were not taken into account in the present study. An evaluation of the effectiveness of the respective techniques was carried out on the basis of the five tests mentioned above.

3. Results

Six measurements were taken for the purpose of the present study: three were performed prior to each procedure and three upon each procedure. Each of the six measurements consisted in performing the five tests mentioned above.

A positive result in all five tests was a necessary condition for qualifying the patient into the study group. Upon evaluating the entire group, it turned out that each time when the procedure brought about a removal of pelvic torsion, the results of all five tests were negative. Since the results for all five tests were identical, positive results in all five tests were treated as a single positive result, while negative results in all five tests were treated as a single negative result. This is also how the results have been described in the present paper.

Initially, all study subjects showed pelvic torsion. Upon the administration of the last procedure, regardless of the method used, the pelvic torsion subsided in all patients. The dynamics of subsidence is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Percentage of patients diagnosed with pelvic asymmetry, classified by procedure number and method used.

As the data show, the methods are characterized by similar effectiveness. However, Cyriax's method proved to be slightly more effective than the others. This can be read more precisely from Table 1, presenting the number of patients with diagnosed asymmetry in the positioning of the pelvis, classified according to the number of the procedure and the method used.

Table 1. The number of patients diagnosed with pelvic torsion before and after the procedure: data for Cyriax's method, Mulligan's method and Yumeiho.

Measurement no.	Method			Collective result
	Cyriax	Mulligan	Yumeiho	
Procedure 1 – before	15	15	15	45
Procedure 1 – after	0	1	1	2
Procedure 2 – before	11	12	11	34

Procedure 2 – after	0	0	0	0
Procedure 3 – before	6	8	9	23
Procedure 3 – after	0	0	0	0

For each measurement, neither Mulligan’s method nor Yumeiho were ever more effective than Cyriax’s method, and they at best showed the same effectiveness. The most marked advantage of Cyriax’s method became evident prior to the third procedure.

At this stage, pelvic asymmetry was found only in six patients. In Mulligan’s group there were eight such patients, and nine in the Yumeiho group.

Despite the fact that Cyriax’s method proved to be evidently more effective for the group studied, one must bear in mind that this may have been accidental. It was decided that a statistical analysis of the differences between the effectiveness of all of the methods would be carried out by a chi-square distribution test for each measurement. For the chi-square test, a table with theoretical numbers was prepared for each measurement. Then the chi-square statistic was calculated and the chi-square critical value was found in the tables for the accepted significance level of 0.05 and three degrees of freedom. Features X (presence or absence of the symptom) and Y (type of therapy) may be considered independent if the critical value is greater than the chi-square value found.

Results obtained:

Measurement after the first procedure: the calculated value of chi-square is 1.046; the critical value of the chi-square test found in the tables is 7.815.

Measurement prior to procedure two: the calculated value of chi-square is 0.24; the critical value of the chi-square test found in the tables is 7.815.

The measurement after procedure two yielded identical results for all methods; the lack of differences was an unequivocal result in itself – there was no need to perform a chi-square test.

Measurement prior to procedure three: the calculated value of chi-square is 1.24; the critical value of the chi-square test found in the tables is 7.815.

The measurement after procedure three, as after procedure two, yielded identical results for all three methods, hence there was no need to perform a chi-square distribution test.

The above results indicated that in each case the value of the chi-square statistic calculated was less than the critical value, which showed that **there were no statistically significant differences between the efficiency of the therapeutic methods examined.**

Simultaneously, the study proved that all three manual therapy methods worked well to remove pelvic torsion in patients. After procedure one, only two in 45 patients (4.4%) showed pelvic torsion (a collective result for all three methods). After six to seven days, prior to procedure two, 34 patients (75%) exhibited pelvic torsion, and none of them did after the second procedure. Prior to the last procedure – the third procedure in the series – pelvic torsion was diagnosed in 23 patients (51.1%). We may conclude that there is a tendency for the dysfunction of pelvic torsion to subside. In four patients (8.9%) it was observed that the pelvic asymmetry did not occur prior to procedure two (no manual procedures were used), and after another six- to seven- day period, pelvic asymmetry was again observed in a certain patient. This asymmetry may be an individual characteristic, resulting from the patient’s daily lifestyle, and may depend on whether or not the patient is active physically, and on the kind of work and mobility the patient may engage in daily, etc.

The study of the 45-person group revealed that an overwhelming majority, i.e. 41 patients (91.1%) exhibited pelvic torsion, so that a palpation test showed the right superior posterior spine to be positioned higher than the left. Looking at the patient from the front, we observed the reverse situation: here the right anterior superior spine was positioned higher than the left. Only in four out of 45 patients (8.9%) the pelvis was turned in the opposite direction, so that the left superior posterior iliac spine was positioned higher than the right one, while at the front, the left anterior superior spine was situated lower than the right one. One-third of the patients in the study group had scoliosis.

4. Discussion

All three therapeutic methods bring positive results with regard to removing pelvic asymmetry, although each of the methods utilizes different techniques addressing the sacroiliac joints. For this reason, each of the

methods has somewhat different strengths and weaknesses.

In Yumeiho, the manipulation of the lumbar, sacral and iliac segments selected by Masayuki Saionji is characterized by high effectiveness. Regardless of the direction of pelvic torsion, the manipulation is always performed in the same planes (Saionji 1996). Performing the manipulation on a mattress ensures patient comfort. A quality of this technique that may be considered a disadvantage is using long leverage, whereby not only the sacroiliac joints, but also other spinal structures are engaged. This quality may however also be an advantage, when there are related pathologies in the lumbar and sacroiliac region –then this single technique allows obtaining a therapeutic result in both regions. What may be considered another disadvantage of Yumeiho is lack of an equally effective replacement technique which might be used if it were impossible to perform the first manipulation. A significant advantage of Yumeiho in removing pelvic torsion is the shortness of a single procedure – it is shortest of all three methods – and the effort exerted by the therapist is relatively low.

In Mulligan's method, the mobilizations used with movement to treat sacroiliac joints are generally considered safe for the patient, and they are well-tolerated. However, when the pelvic torsion is significant, it often becomes necessary to apply more than one technique, i.e. perform mobilization when the patient is standing up and lying down. The standing mobilization is carried out with the patient walking (Mulligan 2004). In patients moving chaotically and poorly cooperating with the therapist, the execution of the technique and maintenance of the appropriate slide within the sacroiliac joints may result in significantly burdening the therapist, thus making the technique rather cumbersome.

In Cyriax's method, both mobilizations and manipulations are used. These techniques, as demonstrated by the present study, bring good therapeutic results. The variety of available techniques allows therapists to use them interchangeably, adjusting the selection to the specific needs of a given patient. Cyriax's method is the oldest of the three; the first book, titled *Deep massage and manipulation*, was published in 1944. Some of the techniques included in this method are now deemed obsolete by modern therapists. The disadvantages of this method include those techniques which are characterized by rather demanding therapeutic positions and rather long levers that are employed in Cyriax's method relatively frequently (Cyriax 1984).

It is worth quoting here the result of the study carried out by Tullberg, Blomberg, Branth, and Johnsson, described in the 1998 issue of *Spine*. The study showed no effects after manipulation and/or mobilization in the form of a lasting change in the relative position of the ilium and the sacrum (the result was confirmed by x-ray stereophotogrammetry). Despite that, the authors are convinced that, regardless of whether or not the manipulation changed the position of the sacroiliac joint, "something" did change in the joints due to manipulation. This was reflected by high scores in the evaluation of pelvic statics, which normalized upon manipulation. This is to say that evaluation tests of the height of the alae, the anterior superior spines and posterior superior spines, with the patient prone, lying on the back, and standing, showed that the original difference in the height of the anterior and/or posterior spines disappeared upon manipulation. Additionally, the authors noted that the manipulation or mobilization might affect the articular capsulae surrounding the sacroiliac joint, the muscles and ligaments as well as the neuromuscular reflexes of the posture (Tullberg i wsp.1998).

Studies of the sacroiliac joint continue to be an open area of exploration. The available reports fall short of exhausting the subject, and in order to confirm the credibility of functional tests, further studies are no doubt required. The tests of sacroiliac joints utilized in this study are among the ones most frequently used by manual therapists. Despite this, they are an imperfect therapeutic method, and they leave a vast area for exploration and growth in the field of manual therapy.

5. Conclusions

The analysis carried out demonstrated no significant differences between the therapeutic methods included in the study: the methods of Mulligan, Cyriax and Saionji Yumeiho. No statistically significant differences were observed for any of the measurements taken (significance level of 0.05). Thus, the result of the study allows drawing the conclusion that all three manual therapy methods show similar effectiveness in treating pelvic torsion in patients. Additionally, the study proved that the manual therapy methods investigated here are effective in treating sacroiliac joints.

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